

WHO Guidelines for malaria

Systematic reviews, background papers and other unpublished evidence considered in the development of recommendations

Prevention/Preventive chemotherapies

Section

4.2.4 Intermittent preventive treatment of malaria in school-aged children (IPTsc). In *WHO Guidelines for malaria*, 3 June 2022.

Title

AMSTAR checklist: Preventive malaria treatment among school-aged children in sub-Saharan Africa: a systematic review and meta-analyses

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AMSTAR Checklist: Preventive malaria treatment among school-aged children in sub-Saharan Africa: a systematic review and meta-analyses.

Cohee LM, Opondo C, Clarke SE, et al. *The Lancet Global Health* 2020; **8**(12): e1499-e511.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2214109X20303259?via%3Dihub>

PROSPERO: CRD42016030197

https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/prospero/display_record.php?RecordID=30197

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In order to assess the validity of the study above we first re-ran the initial search. This yielded 883 references (the original found 839), including 271 duplicates (initially 211), for a total of 612 unique articles (compared to 628 in Cohee et al.). While the numbers don't match exactly with the numbers in the study Prisma diagram, in consultation with the CDC librarian, we determined that regular database maintenance and updates can account for differences of this magnitude and that the initial search was comprehensive. Therefore, we did not re-screen the initial list of studies.

We additionally ran a search with the same search terms, but from Dec 15, 2018 (the final date included by Cohee et al.) to 12/23/2021. This yielded a total of 204 articles, with 54 duplicates, for a total of 150 unique articles. Of these 150 articles, 149 were excluded: 132 were the wrong intervention (not intermittent preventive treatment), 7 were the wrong patient population, 3 articles were already included in Cohee et al., 2 were modelling studies, 2 were ongoing trials, 1 was a duplicate study population, 1 article had the wrong outcomes, and 1 was a review article. The one study which potentially provides additional data is "Impact of Three-Year Intermittent Preventive Treatment Using Artemisinin-Based Combination Therapies on Malaria Morbidity in Malian Schoolchildren" by Maiga et al., *Trop Med Infect Dis* 2020;5(3):148 <https://doi.org/10.3390/tropicalmed5030148>. This article reports on the same study population as Barger et al. (*TMIH* 2009; 14(7):784-91) which was previously included in the Cohee review, but includes additional follow up (September 2007-May 2008 in Barger et al, September 2007-January 2010 in the newer paper by Maiga et al.). This trial, in Kollo, Mali, followed children 6-13 years old randomized to receive two annual rounds of sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine-artesunate (SPAS), amodiaquine-artesunate (AQ+AS), or control (vitamin C 250 mg tablet in 2007, water only in subsequent years). Out of an initial 296 children enrolled in Sept 2007, 243 provided data in 2008 (2 lost to follow-up and 53 aged out of the study), and 184 provided data in 2009 (59 aged out). The prevalence of asymptomatic parasitemia was lower in the SP+AS compared to control (38 (7.5%) vs. 143 (28.7%); and 47 (12.7%) vs. 75 (21.2%); $p < 0.002$) in 2007 and 2008, respectively. Hemoglobin concentration was significantly higher in children receiving SP+AS (11.96, 12.06, and 12.62 g/dL) than in control children (11.60, 11.64, and 12.15 g/dL; $p < 0.001$) in 2007, 2008, and 2009, respectively (Figure 1). No impact on clinical malaria was observed (data on malaria cases shown in Figure 2; all

cause clinic visits Figure 3). While the results in year one that were included in the Cohee et al. review demonstrated a substantial difference among children receiving IPTsc vs placebo, the magnitude of effect decreased in subsequent years. Additionally, given the decreasing sample sizes, each additional year contributes less to the overall analysis. Thus, addition of this data will not substantially impact the overall conclusion of the review.

The AMSTAR review of Cohee et al. demonstrated that the review was of sufficient quality and our additional search for articles through December 2021 did not identify any new study populations. Inclusion of the one newly identified article does not substantively change the conclusions of the Cohee et al. review.

Table 1. Outcomes among 11 studies included in the Cohee et al. individual patient data meta-analysis

Outcome	Number of studies	Intervention (n/N)	Control (n/N)	ADJUSTED Relative risk (95% CI)
Plasmodium falciparum infection/prevalence	11	869/ 8437	2521/ 7221	0.46 (0.40, 0.53)
Anaemia	11	1855/ 8113	1904/ 6827	0.85 (0.77, 0.92)
Risk of clinical malaria during follow up	4	134/1178	144/637	0.50 (0.36, 0.60)

Figure 1. Graphic abstract reproduced from Maiga et al, 2020, showing the mean hemoglobin level in intervention arms (SP+AS (panel A) and AQ+AQ (panel B)) versus control in 2007, 2008, and 2009.

Figure 2. Maiga et al 2020, malaria cases by year

a. SPAS vs control.

b. AQAS vs control.

Figure 3. Maiga et al 2020, All-cause clinic visits by year

a. SPAS vs control.

b. AQAS vs control.

Results from the use of the AMSTAR tool on the Cohee review are included below.

<p>1. Did the research questions and inclusion criteria for the review include the components of PICO?</p>		
<p>For Yes: -</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Population <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Intervention <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Comparator group <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Outcome 	<p>Optional (recommended)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Timeframe for follow-up 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The intervention specified by the Cohee review was preventive malaria treatment, however, they included data from Halliday et al (2014) which assessed a screen and treat strategy. This does not fit with the objectives of the current review. A sensitivity analysis excluding both Halliday et al. 2014 and Rehman et al. 2019 (school-based results from the main study published as Staedke et al. 2018; coverage of the intervention was low) was performed and the exclusion of these studies does not substantially alter the conclusions. The adjusted effect of antimalarial treatment of asymptomatic school-aged children on <i>P. falciparum</i> infection was 0.46 (95% confidence interval (CI) 0.40-0.53) including all studies and 0.42 (95% CI 0.33-0.50) excluding Halliday and Rehman. The effect on anemia overall was 0.85 (95% CI 0.77-0.92) and 0.79 (95% CI 0.70-0.87) excluding Halliday and Rehman. For clinical malaria the adjusted relative risk (95% CI) was 0.50 (0.39-0.60) overall and 0.50 (0.39-0.60) excluding Halliday and Rehman.</p>		
<p>2. Did the report of the review contain an explicit statement that the review methods were established prior to the conduct of the review and did the report justify any significant deviations from the protocol?</p>		
<p>For Partial Yes: The authors state that they had a written protocol or guide that included ALL the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> review question(s) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> a search strategy <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> inclusion/exclusion criteria <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> a risk of bias assessment 	<p>For Yes: As for partial yes, plus the protocol should be registered and should also have specified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> a meta-analysis/synthesis plan, if appropriate, <i>and</i> <input type="checkbox"/> a plan for investigating causes of heterogeneity <input type="checkbox"/> justification for any deviations from the protocol 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partial Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The review was registered at PROSPERO: CRD42016030197. The protocol at PROSPERO does not detail the specific plan for investigating heterogeneity, however this is justified in the supplement and is appropriate. We did not identify substantial deviations from the protocol.</p>		
<p>3. Did the review authors explain their selection of the study designs for inclusion in the review?</p>		
<p>For Yes, the review should satisfy ONE of the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> <i>Explanation for including only RCTs</i> <input type="checkbox"/> OR <i>Explanation for including only NRSI</i> <input type="checkbox"/> OR <i>Explanation for including both RCTs and NRSI</i> 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

4. Did the review authors use a comprehensive literature search strategy?

For Partial Yes (all the following):

- searched at least 2 databases (relevant to research question)
- provided key word and/or search strategy
- justified publication restrictions (e.g. language)

For Yes, should also have (all the following):

- searched the reference lists / bibliographies of included studies
- searched trial/study registries
- included/consulted content experts in the field
- where relevant, searched for grey literature
- conducted search within 24 months of completion of the review

- Yes
- Partial Yes
- No

5. Did the review authors perform study selection in duplicate?

For Yes, either ONE of the following:

- at least two reviewers independently agreed on selection of eligible studies and achieved consensus on which studies to include
- OR two reviewers selected a sample of eligible studies and achieved good agreement (at least 80 percent), with the remainder selected by one reviewer.

- Yes
- No

6. Did the review authors perform data extraction in duplicate?

For Yes, either ONE of the following:

- at least two reviewers achieved consensus on which data to extract from included studies
- OR two reviewers extracted data from a sample of eligible studies and achieved good agreement (at least 80 percent), with the remainder extracted by one reviewer.

- Yes
- No

7. Did the review authors provide a list of excluded studies and justify the exclusions?

For Partial Yes:

- provided a list of all potentially relevant studies that were read in full-text form but excluded from the review

For Yes, must also have:

- Justified the exclusion from the review of each potentially relevant study

- Yes
- Partial Yes
- No

8. Did the review authors describe the included studies in adequate detail?

For Partial Yes (ALL the following):

- described populations
- described interventions
- described comparators
- described outcomes
- described research designs

For Yes, should also have ALL the following:

- described population in detail
- described intervention in detail (including doses where relevant)
- described comparator in detail (including doses where relevant)
- described study's setting
- described timeframe for follow-up

- Yes
- Partial Yes
- No

<p>9. Did the review authors use a satisfactory technique for assessing the risk of bias (RoB) in individual studies that were included in the review?</p>		
<p>RCTs For Partial Yes, must have assessed RoB from</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> unconcealed allocation, <i>and</i> lack of blinding of patients and assessors when assessing outcomes (unnecessary for objective outcomes such as all-cause mortality)</p>	<p>For Yes, must also have assessed RoB from:</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> allocation sequence that was not truly random, <i>and</i> selection of the reported result from among multiple measurements or analyses of a specified outcome</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partial Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Includes only NRSI</p>
<p>NRSI For Partial Yes, must have assessed RoB:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> from confounding, <i>and</i> <input type="checkbox"/> from selection bias</p>	<p>For Yes, must also have assessed RoB:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> methods used to ascertain exposures and outcomes, <i>and</i> <input type="checkbox"/> selection of the reported result from among multiple measurements or analyses of a specified outcome</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partial Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Includes only RCTs</p>
<p>10. Did the review authors report on the sources of funding for the studies included in the review?</p>		
<p>For Yes</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Must have reported on the sources of funding for individual studies included in the review. Note: Reporting that the reviewers looked for this information but it was not reported by study authors also qualifies</p>		<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>11. If meta-analysis was performed did the review authors use appropriate methods for statistical combination of results?</p>		
<p>RCTs For Yes:</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> The authors justified combining the data in a meta-analysis <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> AND they used an appropriate weighted technique to combine study results and adjusted for heterogeneity if present. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> AND investigated the causes of any heterogeneity</p>		<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> No meta-analysis conducted</p>
<p>For NRSI For Yes:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> The authors justified combining the data in a meta-analysis <input type="checkbox"/> AND they used an appropriate weighted technique to combine study results, adjusting for heterogeneity if present <input type="checkbox"/> AND they statistically combined effect estimates from NRSI that were adjusted for confounding, rather than combining raw data, or justified combining raw data when adjusted effect estimates were not available <input type="checkbox"/> AND they reported separate summary estimates for RCTs and NRSI separately when both were included in the review</p>		<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> No meta-analysis conducted</p>

<p>12. If meta-analysis was performed, did the review authors assess the potential impact of RoB in individual studies on the results of the meta-analysis or other evidence synthesis?</p>	
<p>For Yes:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> included only low risk of bias RCTs</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OR, if the pooled estimate was based on RCTs and/or NRSI at variable RoB, the authors performed analyses to investigate possible impact of RoB on summary estimates of effect.</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No meta-analysis conducted</p>
<p>13. Did the review authors account for RoB in individual studies when interpreting/ discussing the results of the review?</p>	
<p>For Yes:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> included only low risk of bias RCTs</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OR, if RCTs with moderate or high RoB, or NRSI were included the review provided a discussion of the likely impact of RoB on the results</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>14. Did the review authors provide a satisfactory explanation for, and discussion of, any heterogeneity observed in the results of the review?</p>	
<p>For Yes:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> There was no significant heterogeneity in the results</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OR if heterogeneity was present the authors performed an investigation of sources of any heterogeneity in the results and discussed the impact of this on the results of the review</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>15. If they performed quantitative synthesis did the review authors carry out an adequate investigation of publication bias (small study bias) and discuss its likely impact on the results of the review?</p>	
<p>For Yes:</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> performed graphical or statistical tests for publication bias and discussed the likelihood and magnitude of impact of publication bias</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No meta-analysis conducted</p>
<p>16. Did the review authors report any potential sources of conflict of interest, including any funding they received for conducting the review?</p>	
<p>For Yes:</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> The authors reported no competing interests OR</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> The authors described their funding sources and how they managed potential conflicts of interest</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p>

AMSTAR Checklist from: Shea BJ, Reeves BC, Wells G, Thuku M, Hamel C, Moran J, Moher D, Tugwell P, Welch V, Kristjansson E, Henry DA. AMSTAR 2: a critical appraisal tool for systematic reviews that include randomised or non-randomised studies of healthcare interventions, or both. *BMJ*. 2017 Sep 21;358:j4008.

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